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THE CLIMATE OF THE SAMUR-DAVACHI PHYSICAL-GEOGRAPHICAL REGION: CHANGES AND RESULTING IMPACTS

Abstract. *The climate of Azerbaijan, as well as the Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region, is influenced by factors such as geographic location, relief, atmospheric circulation, wind regime, solar radiation, and more. Located in the northeastern part of Azerbaijan and on the coast of the Caspian Sea, the climate of the Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region is characterized by semi-desert and arid steppe conditions. The location along the Caspian Sea influences the formation*

of the climate. Winters are mild, while summers are hot and dry. The average annual temperature ranges from 13-15°C, and the annual number of sunny hours is 2200. The annual solar radiation is 125-130 kcal/sm². The total amount of precipitation throughout the year is 300-400 mm, with most of the precipitation falling in the winter and autumn months. The Samur-Dəvəçi region mainly experiences wind from the north, northeast, south, southwest, west, and the brize winds. The climate of the area is characterized by a mild and stable temperature regime. The abundance of sunny hours and the low level of precipitation contribute to drought-like conditions in the region. In recent years, changes in the climate of Azerbaijan, as well as in the physical-geographical region, have been observed. Over the last few years, the average annual temperature has increased by 1-1.5°C. This increase is primarily due to the rise in the number of extreme hot days during the summer. There has also been a decrease in snow cover during the winter months in the Samur-Dəvəçi region. Additionally, the decreasing water levels in the Samur River, which is widely used for irrigation, are a result of negative climatic changes. To mitigate climate change, it is advisable to use artificial irrigation systems, expand forest and green areas, and implement various international measures.

Key words: *Samur-dəvəçi physical-geographical region, climate, climate change, geographic location, relief, solar radiation, atmospheric circulation, wind regime, average annual precipitation and temperature*

КЛИМАТ САМУР-ДАВАЧИНСКОГО ФИЗИКО-ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКОГО РЕГИОНА: ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНЫЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ

Аннотация. *Формирование климата Азербайджана, а также физико-географического района Самур-Девечи, зависит от таких факторов, как географическое положение, рельеф, атмосферная циркуляция, режим ветров, солнечная радиация и другие. Расположенный в северо-восточной части Азербайджана, на побережье Каспийского моря, климат физико-географического района Самур-Девечи характеризуется как полупустынный и сухой степной климат. На формирование климата влияет его расположение вдоль побережья Каспийского моря. Зима здесь мягкая, а лето жаркое и сухое. Среднегодовая температура составляет 13-15°C, а количество солнечных часов в год — 2200 часов. Годовая солнечная радиация составляет 125-130 ккал/см². Годовое количество осадков составляет 300-400 мм, при этом осадки преимущественно выпадают зимой и осенью. В районе Самур-Девечи в основном наблюдаются северные, северо-восточные, южные, юго-западные и западные ветры, а также бризовые ветры. Климат региона отличается мягким и стабильным температурным режимом. Большое количество солнечных часов и малое количество осадков способствуют возникновению проблемы засухи в этом районе. В последние годы в Азербайджане, а также в физико-географическом районе Самур-Девечи наблюдаются определенные изменения климата. За последние годы среднегодовая температура повысилась на 1-1,5°C. Это связано с увеличением числа экстремально жарких дней летом. Также в районе Самур-Девечи наблюдается снижение снежного покрова в зимний период. Снижение уровня воды в реке Самур, которая широко используется для орошения, также является следствием негативных изменений климата. Для борьбы с изменениями климата можно использовать искусственные системы орошения, расширять лесные и зелёные зоны, а также предпринимать ряд международных мероприятий.*

Ключевые слова: *Самур-Деведжинский физико-географический район, климат, изменение климата, географическое положение, рельеф, солнечная радиация, атмосферная циркуляция, режим ветров, среднегодовое количество осадков и температура.*

The Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region, located in the northeastern part of Azerbaijan and included in the Greater Caucasus province, has a distinctive climate. The region's climatic formation is primarily influenced by its geographical position. Its location on the slopes of the Greater Caucasus and its proximity to the shores of the Caspian Sea have a significant impact on the climate of Samur-Davachi. The Caspian Sea moderates the climate, softening extreme conditions. The Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region is characterized by a semi-desert and dry-steppe climate, with hot and dry summers and mild winters. Being situated in the continental transition zone of

Azerbaijan’s subtropical belt leads to a high number of sunny hours across the country. This is especially pronounced in lowland areas, including the Samur-Davachi region, where the number of sunshine hours reaches about 2200 annually. The total solar radiation in the area is approximately 125–130 kcal/cm² [1].

Atmospheric pressure varies between mountainous and lowland areas across the country. As altitude increases, atmospheric pressure decreases, resulting in an uneven distribution of pressure between mountainous and lowland regions. On average, in areas at an altitude of 1000 meters, atmospheric pressure is about 900–905 hPa. In the Samur-Davachi region, the atmospheric pressure is approximately 1013 hPa. Atmospheric pressure in the Samur-Davachi region changes not only due to climatic factors but also in relation to elevation above sea level. Since the region is predominantly lowland and its elevation is close to sea level, the atmospheric pressure remains at a moderate level. Some seasonal fluctuations in atmospheric pressure are observed: pressure tends to increase in winter months and decrease in summer months [3].

Table 1.

Variation of Atmospheric Pressure with Altitude in the Samur-Davachi Physical-Geographical Region

Altitude (metres)	Atmospheric pressure (hPa)
0 (at sea level)	1013
200	990
500	954
1000	899
1500	845

The main factor influencing the climate of the physical-geographical region is its location along the coast of the Caspian Sea. The sea moderates the climate, preventing the air from becoming excessively hot in summer and too cold in winter. The average annual temperature in the Samur-Davachi region ranges between approximately 13–15°C. There are noticeable differences in temperature between winter and summer months. July is the hottest month, while January is the coldest. During summer, air temperatures range from 25–28°C, and in winter, from 2–4°C. Occasionally, winter temperatures can drop to 0°C, while in summer they can reach up to 35°C. The absolute maximum temperature recorded is 43°C, and the absolute minimum is -22°C. Due to the region’s mild climate, sharp temperature fluctuations are not common. The sea contributes to milder summers and cooler winters [1,3].

Another factor shaping the climate of the Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region is the presence of winds in the area. The main factors influencing wind formation are the region’s relief and its location along the coastal zone of the Caspian Sea. In general, the following types of winds are present in the Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region:

1. Breeze winds: Typical of the Caspian Sea coastal zone, breeze winds also affect the Samur-Davachi region. During summer, especially in the hot months of July and August, breeze winds bring cool air masses from the Caspian, refreshing the coastal part of the region.

2. North and northeast winds: Also known as Khazri winds, these are the most common in the region. These winds lower the air temperature, causing cooling, and are mostly observed in winter. North and northeast winds bring not only cold but also humid air, resulting in rainy and cold weather conditions. These winds enter the region from the Caspian Sea.

3. South and southwest winds (Gilavar winds): These winds come from the Absheron direction. Unlike the north and northeast winds, the south and southwest winds raise the air temperature, bringing warm and dry air masses. Mostly observed in summer, these winds sometimes carry dry and dusty air masses as well.

4. West winds: Unlike the other mentioned winds, west winds have less impact on the region. They do not cause sharp temperature changes and are mostly observed in spring and autumn [6].

Another factor contributing to the formation of the climate is the amount of precipitation. The Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region receives approximately 300–400 mm of precipitation annually. Depending on altitude, the average annual amount of precipitation can sometimes reach up to 600 mm. Precipitation is more common in autumn and winter months. The low amount of precipitation is a key factor in the semi-arid climate of the region.

In recent years, certain changes have been observed in the climate of Azerbaijan in general, as

well as in the Samur-Davachi physical-geographical region. There are a number of global and local factors contributing to these negative changes. Anthropogenic factors also have some impact on climate changes. First and foremost, temperature can be mentioned. Both across Azerbaijan as a whole and specifically in the Samur-Davachi region, an increase in temperature has been observed from the end of the 20th century into the early 21st century. According to studies, the temperature has risen by about 1–1.5°C. Notably, rising temperatures in summer reduce the area covered by snow in mountainous regions, which directly affects river levels by lowering them. In addition, rising temperatures in summer accelerate the evaporation of water resources. The increase in temperature also creates a risk of drought. This directly impacts the region’s agriculture negatively [2,9].

Another change occurring in the climate is the amount of precipitation in the region. Currently, a decrease in precipitation is being observed. The uneven distribution of precipitation across seasons also contributes to climate changes. Low precipitation impacts water resources and the established river network in the area. Specifically, a decrease in water resources, a weakening of river flow, and certain problems in the irrigation process are noticeable. Low precipitation is also one of the factors that contribute to drought [7].

The climate of the Samur-Devechi physiographic region is most significantly influenced by the Caspian Sea, as we know. Along with its positive effects, the Caspian Sea also has negative impacts, and changes in its water level are reflected in the region’s climate. Fluctuations in the Caspian Sea’s level, particularly its decline, affect the dynamics of the area’s ecosystem. In addition to the ecosystem, the decreasing water level also leads to land subsidence and the waterlogging of the region’s coastal zone.

The activity of wind is clearly evident in the Samur-Devechi region. In this area, where eolian processes dominate, the number of windy days has been steadily increasing in recent years. This creates conditions for desertification as well as a rise in dust storms. In Samur-Devechi, which already has a climate prone to aridity, such negative effects of wind contribute to climatic changes.

Climate change is driven not only by natural factors but also by human activity—in other words, anthropogenic influences. Anthropogenic impacts are also observable in the Samur-Devechi physiographic region. Human activities here, such as deforestation, the prioritization of agriculture, the establishment of unsuitable agricultural lands, industrialization, urbanization, and similar factors, create conditions for adverse climatic changes. When land is not used properly, soil degradation accelerates. Similarly, improper irrigation systems cause more harm than good to the soil [1].

As a result, it can be stated that the negative changes in climate and their consequences, both in other regions of Azerbaijan and in the Samur-Dəvəçi physical-geographical region, adversely affect not only the physical-geographical structure of the area but also its socio-economic life. Soil degradation, erosion and salinization, loss of biodiversity—in other words, the destruction of the area’s flora and fauna—the reduction of precipitation in river networks and other water resources, the decrease of water bodies due to rising temperatures, desertification, and both natural and anthropogenic factors leading to the decline of forest areas and increasing droughts are among the negative climatic outcomes observed in the Samur-Dəvəçi region in recent years. In order to adapt to these climate changes, mitigate their consequences, and minimize their impacts, it is essential to implement measures at both regional and national levels [1,2].

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DROUGHT DYNAMICS IN THE VALLEY OF RASHT DISTRICT (TAJIKISTAN) UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS

Abstract. The dynamics of the Standardised precipitation index and the Standardised precipitation and evapotranspiration index in Rasht district for the period 1950-2023 is characterised by a constant trend. The results of studies of meteorological conditions of Lakhsh district for the period 1961- 2021 to identify the possibility of drought occurrence are presented. The trend of the drought indices shows an increase in humidity over the period 1961-2021. Despite the positive trend in humidity over the period considered, extreme and severe droughts of varying duration have been observed.

Keywords: drought, Rasht, precipitation, temperature, SPI, SPEI, correlation

ДИНАМИКА ЗАСУХИ В ДОЛИНЕ РАШТСКОГО РАЙОНА (ТАДЖИКИСТАН) В УСЛОВИЯХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ КЛИМАТА

Аннотация. Динамика стандартизированного индекса осадков и стандартизированного индекса осадков и эвапотранспирации в Рахтском районе за период 1950-2023 гг. характеризуется постоянным трендом. Представлены результаты исследований метеорологических условий Лахшского района за период 1961- 2021 гг. с целью выявления возможности возникновения засухи. Тенденция изменения индексов засухи показывает увеличение влажности за период 1961-2021 гг. За рассмотренный период несмотря на положительную тенденцию изменения влажности наблюдаются экстремальные и сильные засухи различной продолжительности.

Ключевые слова: засуха, Рахт, осадки, температура, SPI, SPEI, корреляция

Introduction. Drought one of the manifestations of emergencies is a serious problem for Central Asia. Experts estimate that more than 70 percent of the region's territory is considered vulnerable to natural disasters. Droughts are less frequent than floods but affect more people. Over the past decade droughts have affected 60 per cent of the population exposed to extreme weather events. Droughts are expected to become more frequent in Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan due to prognoses temperature increases and longer periods of extreme heat and evaporation in areas with less precipitation [1, 2].

Continued glacier melt and reduced snow cover will exacerbate water resource problems in Central Asia. In addition, high temperatures and intense precipitation will lead to more frequent and intense natural disasters such as droughts, heat waves, floods, landslides, mudslides and avalanches [4].

Materials and Methods. The present work is devoted to monitoring the occurrence of drought in Rasht of the Rasht valley of Tajikistan due to meteorological conditions in the period 1961-2023.

The climate of the Rasht valley depends on its altitude. The altitude creates a valley rich in biodiversity with several agro-ecological zones. Since the beginning of the 20th Century, there has been a steady increase in average temperature of 0.07°C and a change in precipitation trends. Winter precipitation is steadily increasing, while average spring precipitation has remained stable. The meteorological conditions in Rasht district monitoring by use of data from Rasht (39°05'00"N, 70°30'00"E) meteorological station were used.

Results and Discussion. Seasonal distribution of mean annual temperature and precipitation in Rasht district is shown in Figure 1. Fig. 1 shows that the maximum values of temperature and precipitation in Rasht district are observed in summer and spring, respectively, with the peculiarity that, unlike other geographical latitudes, the temperature is kept within moderate limits with abundant precipitation in spring. The observed climatic conditions are considered favorable for the cultivation of a wide range of agricultural products.